

STUDYING THE HYGIENE STATUS AND IMPROVING THE PREVENTION OF DENTAL DISEASES IN SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

School age is characterized by an increase in the child's independence, changes in lifestyle, diet and level of responsibility for one's own health. These factors often lead to irregular tooth brushing, excess carbohydrate consumption, decreased control by adults and missed preventive visits to the dentist.

Relevance of the topic: School age is characterized by an increase in the child's independence, changes in lifestyle, diet and level of responsibility for one's own health. These factors often lead to irregular tooth brushing, excess carbohydrate consumption, decreased control by adults and missed preventive visits to the dentist.

Additional influences are exerted by educational loads, stressful situations, insufficient awareness of parents about the age-related characteristics of dental risk and the lack of sustainable dental education programs in educational institutions.

All this creates favorable conditions for the progression of dental diseases.

The introduction of systematic preventive measures in the school environment requires an integrated approach, including analysis of the hygienic status of students, assessment of the educational environment, identification of risk factors and determination of the level of dental literacy of the family. Scientific research confirms that the effectiveness of prevention increases significantly with a combination of individual education for children, regular professional hygiene, rational fluoride prophylaxis, correction of eating behavior and active pedagogical support. Of particular importance is the interaction between a dentist, parents and teachers, which allows schoolchildren to develop sustainable motivation to follow the rules of oral care and a conscious attitude towards their own health.

The relevance of the study is due to the need to develop and implement modern preventive strategies adapted to the characteristics of school age, increasing the level of dental literacy of the population and creating effective models of interdisciplinary interaction.

A comprehensive study of the hygienic status of schoolchildren and the improvement of preventive programs are the most important conditions for maintaining dental health and creating a culture of hygienic behavior that ensures the well-being of the child in the future.

Purpose of the work: due to the need to develop and implement modern preventive strategies adapted to the characteristics of school age, increasing the level of dental literacy of the population and creating effective models of interdisciplinary interaction based on literary sources.

Materials and methods of research: An analysis of literary sources on the state of hygienic status and improvement of the prevention of dental diseases in school-age children was carried out.

Results of the study: The formation of dental health in schoolchildren is a complex and multifaceted process that depends on a combination of biological, behavioral, socio-pedagogical and medical factors.

At school age, the child gains a higher level of independence, which is reflected in the nature of hygiene skills and commitment to daily oral care. However, actual practice shows that it is during this period that a significant deterioration in hygienic status is observed: irregular morning and evening brushing of teeth, preference for carbohydrate snacks, lack of understanding among many children of the cause-and-effect relationship between hygiene and the development of dental diseases.

This creates the preconditions for the early formation of carious cavities, inflammatory changes in the gums and disorders of enamel mineral metabolism.

A quantitative assessment of the hygienic status is carried out using indices that allow one to analyze the degree of plaque formation, the presence of inflammation and the child's hygienic skills.

Epidemiological studies have revealed that a significant proportion of children of primary school age have indicators corresponding to an unsatisfactory level of hygiene. In adolescents, the situation is aggravated by additional factors: hormonal changes, increased stress and decreased adult control. Particular attention is paid to children from families with a low level of dental literacy, since their parents are not sufficiently oriented in the principles of prevention, the choice of hygiene products and the features of age-related oral care.

An analysis of the eating behavior of schoolchildren shows that the key risk factor is the frequent consumption of sugary drinks, confectionery and foods high in sucrose.

Snacks during breaks often replace a full meal, which leads to multiple fluctuations in pH in the oral cavity and increases the risk of enamel demineralization. Rare consumption of hard foods with a natural structure (vegetables, fruits) reduces the natural self-cleaning ability of teeth.

This behavior becomes typical in the teenage group, which requires the development of new motivational strategies focused on the interests of schoolchildren. Modern approaches to prevention emphasize the need to combine individual, professional and school-pedagogical prevention.

Professional care includes plaque removal, remineralization therapy, fluoridation, fissure sealants and regular caries risk assessment. However, without developed daily skills, these activities are not effective enough. It is important to build a preventive model in which the dentist interacts not only with the child, but also with the educational institution, as well as parents. The most important component is dental education.

Systematic educational modules in schools, including interactive classes, game techniques, multimedia programs and practical training, have proven highly effective. Such activities increase the level of children's knowledge, form correct behavior patterns and significantly improve their hygienic status.

Programs that include repeated training cycles are especially effective, since it is regularity that allows you to consolidate the acquired skills.

Scientific research demonstrates that the motivation of schoolchildren increases several times if preventive activities include elements of competition, collective participation and visual assessment of results.

For example, the use of coloring tablets to determine plaque allows children to independently assess the quality of teeth brushing and adjust the technique. This contributes to the development of responsibility and the formation of internal motivation.

The school environment also has a direct impact on dental health. According to observational data, students in schools where regular preventive programs are carried out demonstrate more favorable hygiene indices and a lower level of carious lesions.

School health workers can play an important role in monitoring oral health, identifying problems early, and referring children to the dentist. The use of an interdisciplinary approach allows us to create a full-fledged prevention system that operates on an ongoing basis.

Conclusion: The analysis of the hygienic status of school-age children confirms that the dental health of this group remains one of the most significant problems of modern preventive medicine.

The high prevalence of caries, gingivitis and other dental diseases is due to a combination of factors: insufficient development of daily hygiene skills, high frequency of carbohydrate snacks, reduced motivation for regular teeth brushing, lack of systematic pedagogical and family control, as well as insufficient availability of professional preventive care.

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